

Adverse soils tolerance

Boron toxicity in rice soils

F. N. Ponnampereuma, principal soil chemist; R. S. Lantin, senior research assistant; and M.T.C. Cayton, research assistant, Soil Chemistry Department, International Rice Research Institute

Although boron toxicity is widely considered a hazard in soils irrigated with high-boron water, literature references to field cases of boron toxicity in rice on such soils could not be found. But now we have evidence for such toxicity.

Boron toxicity is characterized by yellowing of the leaf tips, followed by the appearance of dark-brown elliptical blotches along the leaf edges, which later turn brown and die. Vegetative growth is not seriously depressed unless the toxicity is severe.

Those symptoms were observed on about 7 ha of an 80-ha farm located on soils (mainly Tropaquepts) derived from volcanic ash. The soils had been irrigated for 15 years with deep-well water with a boron content of 3.0–5.3 ppm.

The soils had pH values of 6.6 to 7.8, electrical conductivities (EC) (1:1) of 1.2–4.2 mmho/cm, and an available boron content of 3 to 11 ppm. The corresponding soil analyses for an unirrigated block were pH 5.6, EC 0.03 mmho/cm, and 1.2 ppm available boron, indicating that irrigation had increased alkalinity, salinity, and the boron content of the soils.

The shoot of the affected plants contained 32 to 39 ppm boron at flowering. IR40 showed more tolerance

for boron toxicity than IR8.

Boron toxicity may be an unrecognized factor limiting rice yields on soils irrigated with high-boron water (as is often the case in arid regions) and on soils subject to inundation by seawater (which is high in boron). ■

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